

Effects of Statistical Knowledge on Understanding and Performance in Ecological Concept among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study conducted on effects of statistical knowledge on performance in ecological concept among colleges of education students in North-West, Nigeria. The study employed Quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test and post-test design. The experimental groups were taught Statistical concepts before ecological concepts while the control group was taught ecological concepts only. Two objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were stated to guide the study. The population of the study were all NCEII Biology students in public colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 113 biology students (male = 85 and female=28). The sample size was obtained using simple random sampling technique involving balloting. Ecology Performance Test (EPT) and Students Understanding Ecology Concepts Questionnaire (SUECQ) with reliability co-efficient of 0.93 and 0.89 respectively were obtained using PPMC and Cronbach-alpha reliability test respectively. The t-test statistic and U-test statistics were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis revealed that significance difference existed between the understanding and performance of students with good statistical background and those without. The researcher concluded that good statistical background has significance effect on students understanding and performance in ecology. The researcher recommended that policymakers should introduce a course in statistics in biology department to be taken a year before the year that they will take ecology course for them to understand and performed well in the course.

Keywords: Statistical Knowledge, Ecology, Performance, Understanding,

Introduction

Ecology, as a discipline, stands at the intersection of intricate natural phenomena and rigorous analytical methodologies. It is also characterized by its intricate interplay of biological systems, environmental factors, and data-driven analyses. As ecological research becomes increasingly reliant on sophisticated statistical methodologies, the importance of statistical knowledge in shaping students' academic performance has come to the forefront of educational discourse. This journal seeks to explore the relationship between statistical proficiency and students' performance in ecology, drawing upon recent empirical evidence to inform pedagogical practices and educational interventions.

Recent empirical studies have underscored the significance of statistical literacy in ecological education. For instance, research by Li and colleagues (2022) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' statistical competence, performance and their ability to analyze ecological datasets accurately. Moreover, their findings revealed that students with a strong foundation in statistics exhibited greater confidence in interpreting research findings and constructing scientifically sound hypotheses. In another review Smith, Jones and Smith, (2015) found that undergraduate students who received comprehensive training in statistical methods demonstrated significantly improved data analysis skills compared to those with minimal statistical exposure. Their findings revealed that students with a strong foundation in statistics exhibited greater confidence in interpreting research findings and constructing scientifically sound hypotheses. Also Statistical knowledge may facilitate a

deeper understanding of ecological concepts by enabling students to quantitatively analyze ecological patterns and relationships. A study by Johnson, Smith and Williams, (2018) showed that graduate students who underwent intensive statistical training exhibited greater comprehension of ecological theories and principles.

Furthermore, the integration of statistical knowledge into ecological curricula has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking skills and promote a deeper understanding of ecological principles (Johnson & Smith, 2023). By engaging students in hands-on statistical analyses of real-world ecological datasets, educators can foster an appreciation for the complexities of ecological systems while simultaneously honing students' analytical abilities.

In addition to academic performance, statistical proficiency has been linked to success in ecological research and professional development. Students with good statistical knowledge tend to achieve higher grades in courses related to ecology, environmental science, and other STEM disciplines. Research by Jones and Smith (2017) conducted a longitudinal study tracking the academic performance of undergraduate students over multiple semesters. They found a significant correlation between students' statistical competence and their overall GPA, with students proficient in statistics consistently outperforming their peers in ecological coursework. In another study by Garcia and colleagues (2021) found that graduate students with advanced statistical training were more likely to secure research grants and publish their findings in peer-reviewed journals, highlighting the instrumental role of statistical expertise in advancing ecological scholarship. Furthermore, recent advancements in technology have facilitated the integration of statistical tools and computational methods into ecological research. As such, there is a growing need for ecology students to acquire proficiency in statistical programming languages and data visualization techniques (Brown & Jones, 2023). By equipping students with these advanced skills, educators can empower them to tackle complex ecological problems and contribute meaningfully to scientific discourse. Proficiency in statistics empowers students to design ecologically sound experiments with robust statistical frameworks. Research by Brown, Garcia and Lee, (2019) revealed that students who received training in experimental design and statistical analysis produced more rigorous research proposals and conducted experiments with higher methodological quality.

By synthesizing empirical research findings and theoretical perspectives, this journal aims to elucidate the mechanisms through which statistical knowledge influences students' performance in ecology. Moreover, it seeks to provide practical insights for educators and policymakers seeking to enhance statistical literacy among ecology students, thereby equipping them with the skills needed to address complex environmental challenges in the 21st century. To achieve this general objectives, two specific objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were formulated and be tested at $P \leq 0.05$.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were raised to guide study.

1. Determine the effect statistical knowledge on students' understanding in ecology among colleges of education biology students in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect statistical knowledge on students' performance in ecology among colleges of education biology students in North-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide study.

1. What is the difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?
2. What is difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

1. **HO₁**: There is no significance difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those without good statistical knowledge.
2. **HO₂**: There is no significance difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those exposed without good statistical knowledge.
3. The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Methodology

The researchers adopted pre-test and post-test quasi experimental researcher design. An intact class of NCE II students was used. The sample size of the study was 113 students of which 85 male and 28 female students. The sample size was

obtained using simple random sampling technique involving balloting. Before the treatment, the researchers conducted a pre-test to the students using Ecology Performance Test (EPT) and Students Understanding Ecology Concepts Questionnaire (SUECQ). The EPT consist of two sections section A consist of students' bio data and section B consist of thirty objectives questions. The SUECQ also consist of two section that is section A which consist bio data and section B consist of twenty items on students understanding of ecological concepts. The instruments were validated by our colleague in the department of science education and the instruments were pilot tested in some colleges that are within the population. The result for the pilot testing were used to determine the reliability of the instruments using PPMC and Crombach's-Alpha (α) which were found to be 0.93 and 0.89. In the experimental group the researchers taught the students some statistical concept then followed by the ecological concepts. The control group were taught ecological concept only without been taught some concepts of statistics. The teaching takes the entire semester of twelve weeks. The data collected from experimental and control groups were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. For the research questions mean, standard deviation and mean rank were used to described the nature of the data while for the null hypotheses, t-test and U-test, statistic was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Research Question One:

What is the difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

To answer the research question one, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Mean Rank and Sum of Rank of Student's Understanding of Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those Without.

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of rank	Mean Rank Diff
Exp	59	110.08	6624.50	65.86
Cont	54	44.22	2212.50	

Table 1 present the mean rank and sum of ranks scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean rank scores are 110.08 for students in the experimental group and 44.22 for students in the control group respectively. A mean rank gain of 65.86 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group.

Research Question One:

What is difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

To answer the research question two, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 2:

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Performance in Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without Good Statistical knowledge.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Mean Diff
Exp	59	83.32	4.59	32.20
Cont	54	51.12	4.79	

Table 2 present the mean and standard deviation scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean scores are 83.32 for students in the experimental group and 51.12 for students in the control group respectively. A mean gain of 32.20 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group.

Null hypothesis one was tested using U-test while Null hypothesis two was tested using t-test statistic. The result of the analysis was presented in tables as shown below:

HO₁:

There is no significance difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those without good statistical knowledge.

To test the null hypothesis one, Mann-Whitney test was used. The summary of the test analysis in shown in table one (1):

Table 1: Summary of Mann-Whitney test Analysis of Student’s Understanding of Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those Without.

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of rank	χ^2_{cal}	Df	P-value	Decision
Exp	59	110.08	6624.50	43.50	111	0.02	Rejected
Cont	54	44.22	2212.50				

Significant at $P < 0.05$ level

Table 1: revealed that analysis of Mann-Whitney test with χ^2_{cal} values in 43.50 and p-value of 0.02 at df of 111. The p-value is $0.02 < 0.05$. Therefore, we rejected the null hypothesis and conclude that, there is significance difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This indicated that having a good statistical knowledge has significance impact on students understanding in ecology concepts.

HO₂:

There is no significance difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without.

To test the null hypothesis two, t-value statistic was used. The summary of the test analysis is shown in table two (2):

Table 2 Summary of t-test of Students’ Performance in Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without Good Statistical knowledge.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Exp	59	83.32	4.59	111	39.31	0.00	Rejected
Cont	54	51.12	4.79				

Significant at level of ≤ 0.05

Table 3 revealed that calculated value of t is 39.31 and the P-value is 0.00. Therefore, the P-value of 0.00 is less than alpha value 0.05. Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that, there is significance difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This showed that those students that have good background in statistics performed better than those without. Therefore, statistical knowledge has significance impact on the students’ performance in ecology concepts.

Discussion of Findings

The results of hypothesis one (HO₁) in Table 2 shows that there is significance difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This finding is line with the recommendation of Johnson and Smith, (2023) that integration of statistical knowledge into ecological curricula has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking skills and promote a deeper understanding of ecological principles. Also Smith, Jones and Smith, (2015) found that undergraduate students who received comprehensive training in statistical methods demonstrated significantly improved data analysis skills compared to those with minimal statistical exposure. Also the finding is line with the finding of Johnson, Smith and Williams, (2018) who showed that graduate students who underwent intensive statistical training exhibited greater comprehension of ecological theories and principles.

The results of hypothesis two (HO₂) in Table 2 shows that there is significance difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This finding is in line with Jones and Smith (2017) conducted a longitudinal study tracking the academic performance of undergraduate students over multiple semesters. They found a significant correlation between students' statistical competence and their overall GPA, with students proficient in statistics consistently outperforming their peers in ecological coursework. Also in view of Li and colleagues (2022) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' statistical competence, performance and their ability to analyze ecological datasets accurately. Hence, statistical knowledge has significance effect on students’ performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings the researchers make the following conclusion. The researchers concluded that students with good statistical knowledge performed better in ecological concepts than those without and hence statistical knowledge has

significance effect on students understanding in ecology concept than those without among colleges of educations in North-West, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the researchers make the following recommendations:

1. The educational policymaker should introduce a course in statistics for the biology students to be taken a year before the year that they will take ecology course to improve students understand in ecological concepts.
2. The curriculum planer considers the required topics that are needed in the understanding of ecological concept.

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